

COMPARISON OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES BETWEEN FRTP USING *IN-SITU* POLYMERIZABLE PA6 AND FRP USING FIRST CURABLE EOXY RESIN

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Keywords: *FRTP, ε-caprolactam, first curable epoxy, bending test, Izod impact test*

1 Introduction

Fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) have been used in various fields of structures due to their distinct advantages, namely their light weight, high specific stiffness, high specific strength and so on. Thermosetting resin, a type of matrix of the FRP, changes into permanent cross-linked polymeric structures while it hardens, so that it cannot be re-melted even by heating, and then it is hard to be recycled or reused.

On the other hand, fiber reinforced thermoplastics (FRTP) use a matrix of non cross-linked, straight-chain polymers, and are possible to be re-melted and re-molded by heating. This means that they can be easily recycled and reused. Since materials reducing environmental burdens have been required in the case of the application for automobiles, the FRTP as automobile structural parts must be better than metallic materials with respect to the specific strength and stiffness. In order to obtain the higher strength of the FRTP, they must be developed by using continuous or longer fibers and by increasing the fiber volume content. However, such FRTP cannot be easily fabricated. The thermoplastic resin as the matrix of the FRTP is composed of high polymers having the property of higher viscous even at a higher temperature than their melting points. As a result, the fabrication of the FRTP needs a higher temperature, a higher pressure and a longer process time to allow the matrix to bond with the fibers, unlike the FRP which are easily fabricated due to the use of lower viscous liquid resin as the matrix. Many researchers have studied to overcome these points and some papers¹⁻⁷⁾ are listed in the references.

The authors of this paper have developed the FRTP containing a larger amount of continuous fibers by using the *in-situ* polymerizable polyamide 6⁸⁻¹¹⁾.

This *in-situ* polymerizable polyamide 6 was obtained by using anionic ring-opening polymerization of ε-caprolactam. The FRTP fabricated with a VaRTM had no voids and unfilled resin parts because the ε-caprolactam had very low viscosity before polymerization. The FRTP not only exhibited superior bending properties, but also were suitable for high-speed molding because they could be released from the mold without a cooling process. Furthermore, in order to apply the FRTP for the wider area, the carbon/glass hybrid FRTP using the *in-situ* polymerizable polyamide 6 was fabricated (referred as HFRTP hereinafter), and the bending tests were carried out. As a result, the experimental results of the bending strength and modulus for the HFRTP approximately agreed with the values obtained by the rule of mixture¹²⁾.

In this paper, by using the same VaRTM, the fabrication method of the hybrid FRP (referred as HFRP hereinafter) was demonstrated. The HFRP was composed of the glass and carbon fabrics as the reinforcement and the first curable epoxy resin as the matrix was fabricated. The bending properties and Izod impact strength of HFRP were compared with those of the HFRTP.

2 Fabrication

2.1 Matrix and reinforcement

The matrix of the HFRTP was obtained by using the anionic ring opening polymerizing a monomer of ε-caprolactam with a sodium salt of ε-caprolactam as a catalyst and hexa-methylene diisocyanate (HMDI) as an activator. Its viscosity is very low, and the value is approximately 3 mPa·s at 110°C.

The matrix of the HFRP was the first curable epoxy resin (HICE-11) from Nagase ChemteX Corporation. The viscosity is comparatively lower than the conventional epoxy resin used in CFRP, and the value is 750 mPa·s at 40°C, and 130 mPa·s at 60°C. The common reinforcements of the HFRTM and the HFRP were twilled fabrics of carbon fibers and plain woven textiles of glass fibers. The carbon fabrics have 12.5 tows / 25 mm in both directions of the warp and the weft, and their thickness was 0.22 mm. The thickness of the glass fabrics was 0.21 mm and the fabric density was 20 tows per 25 mm for both directions of the warp and the weft.

2.2 Fabrication method

The catalyst for anionic polymerization of ϵ -caprolactam may lose its catalytic function due to the water in the air whereby polymerization may fail. Therefore, in order to fabricate the HFRTM plate, it may be necessary to use the sealed (air tight) molding methods that can control the water content in the metallic die. This study selected the VaRTM (vacuum assisted resin transfer molding) method in which only a simple vacuum pump was used as a resin infusion system for fabricating the HFRTM and the HFRP plates.

Figure 1 shows a schematic view of the VaRTM system, and Figure 2 is the photograph of the VaRTM apparatus used in this study. After heating the metallic mold dies, the fabrics were placed on the lower die and the interior of the mold dies was decompressed by vacuum pump. In the fabrication of the HFRTM plate, the monomer solution of ϵ -caprolactam was mixed with the catalyst and the activator at 110°C and the mixed monomer solution was injected into the mold dies heated at 140°C. In the fabrication of the HFRP plate, a main agent heated at 50°C was mixed with a curing agent, and it was injected into the mold dies heated at 80°C. The gel times of the *in-situ* polymerizable polyamide 6 and the first curable epoxy resin were within 1 minute and around 6 minutes, respectively.

Figure 3 shows the fabrication process of the HFRTM and the HFRP plates, (a) the heated lower metallic die, (b) piling up the sheets of fabric on the lower die, (c) closing the lower die with the upper metallic die (sealed the mold), and (d) after installing the inlet and outlet tubes, the interior of

metallic die was decompressed until the -90 kPa gauge pressure. Then the resin was injected into the mold by using a vacuum pump. Finally the HFRTM or the HFRP plates were removed from the mold without cooling after lifting the upper die.

Figure 1 Schematic view of VaRTM.

(a) Before fabrication.

(b) During fabrication.

Figure 2 Photographs of the VaRTM apparatus.

COMPARISON OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES BETWEEN FRTP USING IN-SITU POLYMERIZABLE PA6 AND FRP USING RAPID CYCLE HARDENING EPOXY RESIN

(a) Heated lower die.

(b) Placing reinforcements.

(c) Clamping with upper die.

(d) Inlet and outlet tubes.

Figure 3 Fabrication processes of the HFRTTP and the HFRP plates.

Figure 4 and Figure 5 show the fabricated plates of the HFRTTP and the HFRP, respectively. The resin impregnated area of the HFRP plate (330 mm x 430 mm) was smaller than that of the HFRTTP plate (460 mm x 570 mm). Since the viscosity of the first curable epoxy resin is higher than that of the *in-situ* polymerizable polyamide 6, the resin of the first curable epoxy resin could not reached to the wider area within the gel time.

Figure 6 shows laminate sequence of the HFRTTP and the HFRP plates. They consisted of 4 plies of the carbon fabrics in the upper and lower layers and 10 plies of the glass fabrics in the middle layer. Their average fiber volume fractions were 42 %. The cross-sectional views of the HFRTTP and the HFRP plates are shown in Figure 7. They had no voids and unfilled parts, and both plates showed good impregnation of fibers with their matrix.

(a) Surface side (injection side).

(b) Undersurface side.

Figure 4 Fabrication results of the HFRTTP plate.

(a) Surface side (injection side).

(b) Undersurface side.

Figure 5 Fabrication results of the HFRTP plate.

Figure 6 Thickness and laminate sequence of the fabricated HFRTP and HFRP plates.

(a) HFRTP plate.

(b) FRTP plate.

Figure 7 Cross-sectional views of the HFRTP and the HFRP plates.

3 Three-point bending test

In order to compare the bending properties of the HFRTTP and the HFRP specimens, the three-point bending tests were carried out in accordance with JIS K 7017. The specimens had dimensions of the thickness h of 3 mm, a width b of 15 mm, a length l of 100 mm and span length L of 80 mm. The bending stress σ_b and bending strain ε_b were calculated by equation (1) and (2).

$$\sigma_b = \frac{3FL}{2bh^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_b = \frac{6Sh}{L^2} \quad (2)$$

In which F is the load, and S is the center deflection of the specimen.

Table 1 and Table 2 show the bending test results of the HFRTTP and the HFRP specimens. Five specimens were tested for both cases, and then the average values and the coefficient of variations (C.V.) were calculated. Even the average bending strength of the HFRTTP specimens (594 MPa) were same as that of the HFRP specimens (597 MPa), the average failure strain of the HFRTTP specimens (1.68 %) was larger than that of the HFRP specimens (1.57 %). This result means that the interlaminar strength of the HFRTTP specimens between the CF and GF layers was higher than that of the HFRP specimens. Figure 8 shows the representative stress-strain curves.

Table 1 Bending test results of the HFRTTP specimens.

Specimen number	Bending modulus [GPa]	Bending strength [MPa]	Failure strain [%]
1	32.0	558	1.64
2	32.6	628	1.66
3	35.8	604	1.60
4	35.4	594	1.73
5	36.4	585	1.79
Average	34.4	594	1.68
C.V.	4.7%	3.5%	3.7%

Table 2 Bending test results of the HFRP specimens.

Specimen number	Bending modulus [GPa]	Bending strength [MPa]	Failure strain [%]
1	40.2	584	1.48
2	38.8	599	1.57
3	38.4	580	1.59
4	38.6	610	1.63
5	40.0	612	1.57
Average	39.2	597	1.57
C.V.	1.7%	2.0%	2.9%

Figure 8 Comparison between the HFRTTP and the HFRP specimens on stress-strain curves.

4 Izod impact test

In order to compare impact properties of the HFRTTP and the HFRP specimens, the Izod impact tests based on the JIS K 7110 were carried out. The Izod impact apparatus using in this study have impact maximum energy of 5.5 J. The specimen was subjected to an impact by hitting with a hammer to the vertical direction to the surface of the specimen (flat wise impact). The eight kinds of specimens (two resin plates (*in-situ* polymerizable polyamide 6 and first curable epoxy), GFRTTP, GFRP, CFRTTP, CFRP, HFRTTP and HFRP) were fabricated, and their fiber volume fractions were all 42 % except the two resin specimens. Figure 9 shows the specimen installed in the Izod impact apparatus. The specimens had dimensions of the thickness h of 3 mm, a width b of 10 mm, a length l of 80 mm. The impact energy E_n (J) was calculated from the hammer position after the impact, and the Izod impact strength a (kJ/m²) was calculated using E_n

$$\alpha = \frac{E_n}{bh} \times 10^3 \quad (3)$$

Table 3 shows the Izod impact test results of the *in-situ* polymerizable polyamide 6 and the first curable epoxy resin specimens. The symbols of “C”, “H” and “NB” in the following tables mean failure modes of the specimens. The “C” is a complete fracture mode, the “H” is a hinge failure mode, and the “NB” is no breakage. Since the fracture toughness of the *in-situ* polymerizable polyamide 6 is higher, their specimens were not fractured (Figure 10). The average Izod impact strength of the first curable epoxy resin specimens was 5.62 kJ/m², and they were the complete fracture mode as shown in Figure 11.

Table 4 shows the Izod impact test results of the GFRTTP and the GFRP specimens. The average Izod impact strength of the GFRTTP specimen (59.0 kJ/m²) was highest value in all specimens and its value was 4.8 % higher than that of the GFRP specimen (56.3 kJ/m²). The hinge failure mode was observed in both specimens as shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13.

Table 5 shows the Izod impact test results of the CFRTP and the CFRP specimens. The average Izod impact strength of the CFRTP specimen (36.4 kJ/m²) was 15.6 % higher than that of the CFRP specimen (31.5 kJ/m²). In the CFRP specimens, two failure modes (complete and hinge failure mode) were observed. On the other hand, only the hinge failure mode in the CFRTP specimens was observed (Figure 14 and Figure 15).

Table 6 shows the Izod impact test results of the HFRTTP and the HFRP specimens. The average Izod impact strength of the HFRTTP specimen (56.5 kJ/m²) was 8.0 % higher than that of the HFRP specimen (52.3 kJ/m²), and the hinge failure mode was observed in both specimens as shown in Figure 16 and Figure 17. Even the four plies of the CF fabrics were used in the HFRTTP specimen, the impact strength of the HFRTTP specimen showed almost same values of the GFRP specimen. The experimental impact strengths of the HFRTTP and the HFRP specimens were larger than the calculated values (52.4 and 49.0 kJ/m²) based on the Tables 4 and 5 and the rule of mixture.

Figure 9 Specimen installed in the Izod impact apparatus.

Table 3 Izod impact test results of the *in-situ* polymerizable polyamide 6 and the first curable epoxy resin specimens.

Specimen number	Izod impact strength (kJ/m ²)	
	In-situ polymerizable PA6	First curable EP
1	NB	5.59 C
2	NB	5.70 C
3	NB	5.47 C
4	NB	5.87 C
5	NB	5.45 C
Average	—	5.62
C.V.	—	2.8%

Figure 10 Specimen of the *in-situ* polymerizable polyamide 6 after the Izod impact test.

COMPARISON OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES BETWEEN FRTP USING IN-SITU POLYMERIZABLE PA6 AND FRP USING RAPID CYCLE HARDENING EPOXY RESIN

Figure 11 Specimen of the first curable epoxy resin after the Izod impact test.

Table 4 Izod impact test results of the GFRTTP and the GFRP specimens.

Specimen number	Izod impact strength (kJ/m ²)	
	GFRTTP	GFRP
1	57.2 H	55.2 H
2	60.9 H	55.0 H
3	58.3 H	55.9 H
4	59.9 H	58.9 H
5	58.6 H	56.3 H
Average	59.0	56.3
C.V.	2.2%	2.5%

Figure 12 Specimen of the GFRTTP after the Izod impact test.

Figure 13 Specimen of the GFRP after the Izod impact test.

Table 5 Izod impact test results of the CFRTP and the CFRP specimens.

Specimen number	Izod impact strength (kJ/m ²)	
	CFRTP	CFRP
1	40.3 H	32.2 H
2	34.3 H	31.7 C
3	32.8 H	30.2 H
4	39.5 H	32.5 C
5	35.3 H	30.8 H
Average	36.4	31.5
C.V.	8.1%	2.8%

Figure 14 Specimen of the CFRTP after the Izod impact test.

Figure 15 Specimen of the CFRP after the Izod impact test (hinge failure mode).

Table 6 Izod impact test results of the HFRTTP and the HFRP specimens.

Specimen number	Izod impact strength (kJ/m ²)	
	HFRTTP	HFRP
1	59.7 H	52.2 H
2	59.4 H	57.8 H
3	54.9 H	52.6 H
4	54.1 H	51.5 H
5	54.4 H	47.3 H
Average	56.5	52.3
C.V.	4.5%	6.4%

Figure 16 Specimen of the HFRTTP after the Izod impact test.

Figure 17 Specimen of the HFRP after the Izod impact test.

5 Conclusions

In order to apply the FRTP for the wider area, carbon/glass hybrid fabrics were used as the reinforcement and the *in-situ* polymerizable polyamide 6 as the matrix. Furthermore, the HFRP specimens using first curable epoxy resin were fabricated, and their results of three-point bending test and Izod impact test were compared to those of the HFRTTP specimens. The following items were obtained through this study.

- (1) The gel times of the *in-situ* polymerizable polyamide 6 and the first curable epoxy resin were within 1 minute and around 6 minutes, respectively.
- (2) The HFRTTP using the *in-situ* polymerizable polyamide 6 not only were suitable for high-speed molding, but also exhibited higher bending and impact properties than the HFRP using the first curable epoxy resin.
- (3) The average bending strength of the HFRTTP specimens were approximately same as those of the HFRP specimens. However, the average failure

strain of the HFRTTP specimens was larger than that of the HFRP specimens because the interlaminar strength of the HFRTTP specimens between the CF and GF layers was higher than that of the HFRP specimens.

(4) The average Izod impact strength of the HFRTTP specimens was higher than that of the HFRP specimens. The experimental results of the HFRTTP and the HFRP specimens were larger than the calculated values.

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